

INDUSTRIAL ACCEPTANCE OF A NEWLY DEVELOPED SOLAR THERMAL ENERGY SYSTEM APPLIED TO INDUSTRIAL PROCESSES

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Abstract: This study assessed the industrial acceptance of a newly developed Solar Thermal Energy (STE) system called Application of Solar Thermal Energy to Processes (ASTEP), which has three main components: rotating Fresnel solar collectors known as the SunDial, a phase change thermal storage tank, and an electronic control unit. ASTEP can provide thermal energy to industrial processes operating up to and above 400 °C. Furthermore, an environmental and economic assessment showed potential annual reductions of carbon emissions by 900 tonnes and financial savings of €250,000 from the industry. To assess its acceptance for industrial processes, a total of n=318 industrial representatives from both SPIRE and non-SPIRE industries across Europe, North America, Asia, and Oceania were recruited using online surveys and the following categories were assessed; industry type, company size, process type, temperature range, current energy sources, technical compatibility with current processes, opinion on the viability of ASTEP's costs, and anticipated impact on environmental and energy standards. Results showed positive acceptance levels of ASTEP's technical suitability (82%), viability of viability (80%), and expected impact on standards (87%). Acceptance was particularly strong among aerospace, metallic, and automotive industries, as well as among large (84%) and medium-sized (87%) companies. However, lower acceptance among small (37%) and micro-sized (45%) companies was observed due to high upfront costs, highlighting opportunities for financial incentives towards small-scale applications of ASTEP.

Keywords: Solar Thermal Energy, Industrial Acceptance, SPIRE and non-SPIRE Industries

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of Solar Thermal Energy (STE) systems has potential in supplying clean energy to industrial processes, enabling the displacement of fossil fuel-based sources and significantly reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. One such newly developed system, the Application of Solar Thermal Energy to Processes (ASTEP), developed with EU funding, was critically evaluated by Tannous et al. [1] for its potential integration into both SPIRE industrial processes operating at high temperatures exceeding 400 °C and non-SPIRE industrial processes operating within the medium temperature range of 150–400 °C. Their study found that ASTEP is well-suited for these temperature demands, capable of reaching above 400 °C, and holds the potential to deliver annual energy savings of 96.3 TWh across these industries. The ASTEP module consists of three main components: rotating Fresnel solar collectors known as the SunDial, a thermal storage tank, and an electronic control unit [2]. A visual reference is shown in Figure 1 as supplied by Barnetche et. al [3]:

Figure 1: Visual Reference of ASTEP [3]

ASTEP has already been applied to two industries: a steel-tube manufacturing plant in Iasi, Romania and a dairy production plant in Corinth, Greece. Furthermore, an environmental assessment [4] of the ASTEP system demonstrated its potential to reduce industrial reliance on non-renewable energy sources by 60% and decrease greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 900 tonnes. An economic assessment [5] further indicated significant financial benefits, estimating total industry savings of €250,000. Additionally, an analysis conducted within the Italian ceramic industry by Buonomo et al. [6] revealed that ASTEP implementation could reduce CO₂ emissions by 180 tons. Due to these proven technical, environmental, and financial benefits, several authors [7][8] have supported that innovative STE systems are highly attractive to industries aiming to eliminate fossil fuel use within their supply chains. Zafar et. al [7] in particular stated that the industry is keen to implement new STE systems such as ASTEP as these systems effectively meet their process temperature requirements while delivering substantial environmental and economic benefits.

To respond to growing industry interest, Zafar et al. [7] recommended assessing the social industrial acceptance of newly developed STE technologies like ASTEP due to the importance of realizing industrial needs for further deployment. Based on the technical, economic, and environmental aspects of ASTEP discussed in the literature [1][4][5], it can be deduced that its acceptance is influenced by how SPIRE and non-SPIRE industries perceive ASTEP's compatibility with their process requirements within three categories: ASTEP's technical compatibility with existing industrial processes, financial viability of ASTEP's costs and monetary savings, and ASTEP's enhancement of existing environmental and energy standards. A few authors have explored the environmental and economic aspects of industrial acceptance of solar energy systems. For instance, Schriever & Halstrup [9] assessed the industrial acceptance of solar PV systems among 101 German automotive firms, finding that acceptance of PV was influenced by the technology's impact on the industry's compliance with environmental standards. Qamar et al. [10] had conducted an acceptance study amongst 127 industrial representatives from Pakistan's textile industry, and found positive acceptance of STE's thermal output and performance. Furthermore, Kumar et al. [11] surveyed India's food industries regarding STE systems, highlighting strong industrial acceptance based on the technical compatibility of STE with thermal processes operating at and above 400°C. However, Corona & Miguel [8] argued that future studies must move beyond assessments focused on traditional solar systems, while Zafar et al. [4] emphasised the importance of including innovative STE systems such as ASTEP in industrial acceptance studies. Additionally, Kuhnen & Hahn [12] stressed the need for comprehensive assessments across all three mentioned categories to fully understand industrial readiness for STE adoption. Sovacool & Ratan [13] supported that conducting such assessments of industrial acceptance can enhance confidence among industry stakeholders during deployment, thereby accelerating the market penetration of STE systems.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Boundary Conditions

The first part the methodology was to form the boundary conditions for the assessment of industrial acceptance during the potential application of ASTEP to SPIRE and non-SPIRE industries. These industries consist of external industrial stakeholders operating within a medium-temperature range between 150–400°C, originating from food and beverage, textiles, and water treatment industries, as well as representatives operating at high-temperature exceeding 400°C, which include automotive, aerospace, chemical processing, non-metallic minerals, and metallic industries. The stakeholder sample size for this assessment was N=318, distributed across 15 regions as follows: the UK (22), Germany

(22), France (20), Spain (21), Sweden (22), Greece (22), Romania (22), Austria (21), Poland (22), the Czech Republic (22), the US (21), Canada (21), India (19), China (20), and Australia (21).

Next, these targeted industries encompass company sizes defined by employee count: micro enterprises have less than 10 employees, small enterprises have 10–49 employees, medium-sized enterprises have 50–249 employees, and large enterprises have 250 employees or more as defined by (OECD [14]). The representative may hold any of the four positions: managing directors, project managers, technical leads, and HR representatives.

The first assessment category considered the industry's current engagement with energy sources, including the use of renewable and solar energy systems. This category also included examining existing environmental standards for enhancing energy efficiency and reducing emissions. The next assessment category assessed the industrial acceptance of ASTEP's technical compatibility with existing industrial processes in terms of its operating temperature range and thermal energy output. The following category explored the industry's opinion on the viability of ASTEP's costs and benefits from reduced energy expenses, relief from carbon tax schemes, and increased production volumes. The last category assessed ASTEP's anticipated impact on industrial compliance with current environmental standards.

2.2 Data Collection

Data for the industrial acceptance of ASTEP was collected using the online Qualtrics platform (Qualtrics, Seattle, USA) (Miller et al. [15]). The participants for this survey were recruited in accordance with the criteria defined in the Boundary Conditions in section 2.1. All 318 participants from the industry were recruited and provided information about the industries, geographic regions, company sizes, and positions as defined in the Boundary Conditions in section 2.1. This number is sufficient as reported by Witte & Witte [16]. Ethical Approval to conduct the surveys was obtained from Brunel University London.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Breakdown by Industry Type, Size, Processes, and Operating Temperatures

The first result from the assessment is the percent breakdown of industry type as displayed in Figure 2. It can be seen that the majority of the participants belonged to the automotive industry followed by metallic, aerospace, chemical & petrochemical industry then food and beverages, textile and other industries.

Figure 2: Percent Breakdown by Industry Type

With regards to the company sizes from those industries, it was found that 41% were large, 39% were medium sized, 14% were small and 6% were micro. These industries were found to currently operate multiple in-house process types, with the most popular processes being heat treatment (63%), metal curing (52%), sterilisation (46%), and baking (23%). Please note that a single participant was allowed to choose multiple processes, hence their responses overlapped, and the percent breakdown by process type does not add up to 100%. Concurrently, 70% of participants had stated that their process requirement temperatures belonged to the medium temperature range of 150-400 °C, with 63% stating that their processes also use the lower temperature range of 150 °C, and 36% reported that they have processes in the higher temperature range of over 400 °C. Please note that participants may operate multiple processes within multiple temperature ranges, explaining how the total percent exceeds 100.

3.2 Current Energy Use

Table 1 presents the breakdown of energy sources used by the industry.

Table 1: Current Energy Sources for Processes

Energy Source	% of Participants Using This Energy Source
Electric Generators	54%
Electricity via the Grid	52%
Renewable Energy Systems	80%
Gas/Fuel	34%
Solar	74%

It can be seen that the renewable energy systems were the most used energy source by the industry, with 80% of participants using them, followed by electricity from the grid (52%), and gas/fuel (34%). Moreover, 74% of the industry reported using a form of solar energy to power their processes. It was further found that while 39% of industries use Photovoltaic (PV) panels. Please note that the participants were allowed to choose multiple energy sources, which explains how the total percent in Table 1 exceeds 100.

Furthermore, 100% of participants had reported that environmental and energy management standards through ISO14001 and ISO50001 were in place.

3.3 Industrial Acceptance of ASTEP's Technical Compatibility, Costs, & Impact on Standards

Figure 3 presents the industrial acceptance level of ASTEP's technical compatibility.

Figure 3: Acceptance Levels of ASTEP's Technical Compatibility

It can be seen that 82% of the industry has shown positive acceptance of ASTEP's operating temperature and thermal output, perceiving it as highly applicable for their current industrial processes. This was supported by additional comments made in the survey, which mentioned that ASTEP was highly compatible with annealing, tempering, stress relieving, preheating, and sterilisation processes within the 150–400°C temperature range. This result is heavily corroborated by the study of Kumar et. al [11], who had found that the Fresnel solar collectors used by ASTEP are easily capable of providing up to and above 400°C for processes similar to ones reported in this study. They, as a result, had also found high industrial acceptance for STE systems using state-of-the-art Fresnel collectors. Furthermore, of these participants, positive acceptance was mostly shown by the aerospace industry (92%), metallic (89%), automotive (86%), and chemical (76%) for ASTEP's technical performance. This result is again validated by the studies of Verma et al. [17], who found that representatives from these industries had found similar STE technologies to be highly applicable for their operating temperatures. Furthermore, more large (84%), and medium-sized (87%) companies had shown positive acceptance as compared to small (70%) and micro-sized (63%) companies had shown positive acceptance, a trend verified by Qamar et. al [10], who found that larger companies are more willing to invest resources into integrating STE systems.

A few participants from the Mining industry (13%) expressed opportunities to improve the compatibility of ASTEP to their process requirements, with the study of Akofa & Ali [18] finding that representatives from this industry required temperatures in the range of 500-600°C, exceeding the capability of ASTEP at 400°C. Next, 80% of the industry found ASTEP's costs to be viable, with 74% of participants demonstrating strong interest in ASTEP's cost savings in annual energy bills, carbon tax relief, and increase in production volumes. These findings are supported by Kumar et al. [11], who also identified that STE systems offer significant financial savings and carbon tax advantages for industries, while additionally contributing supplementary energy that can boost production volumes. On the other hand, 37% of small and 45% of

micro-sized companies did not find ASTEP's costs to be viable due to the high upfront costs and that it did not fall into their budget, highlighting an opportunity to provide financial subsidies for small-scale applications of ASTEP. This finding is supported by Qamar et al. [10], who noted that subsidies are needed for encouraging STE adoption in small companies. Finally, 87% of the industry anticipated that applying ASTEP would positively impact their compliance with current environmental and energy standards; ISO14001 and ISO50001, respectively. It was further found that this positive view was held amongst 77% of large, 81 % of medium, 70% of small, and 65% of micro sized companies. This enhancement of standards was cited to be attributed to ASTEP's carbon tax relief and energy savings positively contributing to industry's energy efficiency and reducing environmental impact. This finding is corroborated by Kals [19], who found that STE contributes directly to energy efficiency and emissions reduction in industries, leading to greatly improved industrial compliance to ISO 14001 and 50001 standards.

4. CONCLUSIONS

It can be concluded that there is a clear need from the industry to develop advanced STE systems such as ASTEP, capable of achieving higher temperatures, in order to make their industrial processes more environmentally sustainable and economically efficient. This was evidenced by strong acceptance levels for ASTEP's technical compatibility (82%), cost-effectiveness (80%), and its anticipated impact on environmental and energy management systems (87%). The highest levels of acceptance were found among the aerospace, metallic, and automotive industries originating from large and medium-sized companies. However, some reservations were noted among small and micro-sized companies, which perceived the technology as financially unviable due to high upfront investment costs. This highlights the need for more affordable, small-scale STE solutions, hopefully supported by targeted subsidies.

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